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Model analysis to identify companies approaching bankruptcy

KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The article is relevant because the number of company bankruptcies increased, especially in capital-intensive industries such as construction. This creates the need to develop and apply effective methods for the early detection of financial problems, which makes the topic particularly relevant.

The article aims to analyze models for identifying companies approaching bankruptcy.

Materials and methods. The materials were articles in peer-reviewed journals on finance and economics devoted to the analysis of financial ratios and bankruptcy prediction. Research methods included calculating financial coefficients based on financial reporting data and statistical analysis.

Results. A primary duty of an arbitration administrator in the insolvency (bankruptcy) procedure is to conduct a financial analysis of the debtor's activities. The study of the debtor's financial condition was carried out by the approved Rules for performing financial analysis by the arbitration administrator using the coefficient method of economic analysis. The analysis results can be used to substantiate the possibility or impossibility of restoring the debtor's solvency, and the expediency of introducing subsequent procedures used in bankruptcy proceedings.

Conclusion. With the development of technologies such as machine learning and big data, new opportunities are opening up for deeper and more accurate analysis of financial ratios. This allows us to develop more complex bankruptcy prediction models, which makes the topic relevant for researchers and practitioners.

The prospects also lie in the possibility of integrating the analysis of financial coefficients with other methods, such as the analysis of external factors (economic, political, social) and qualitative analysis.

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FOR CITATION

INTRODUCTION

The topic is particularly relevant because in recent years, the number of bankruptcies among companies increased, especially in capital-intensive industries such as construction. This creates the need to develop and apply effective methods for the early detection of financial problems.

The construction industry plays a key role in the world economies. Problems in this area can have serious consequences for related industries and the economy as a whole. Therefore, it is important to identify companies that are on the verge of bankruptcy to prevent economic consequences.

Economic fluctuations, changes in legislation, and external factors such as the COVID-19 pandemic can negatively affect companies' financial condition.

Thus, the topic is relevant, contributes to a deeper understanding of financial risks, and helps develop effective management tools which are of significant importance for the sustainability of companies and the economy as a whole.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials were articles in peer-reviewed journals on finance and economics devoted to the analysis of financial coefficients and bankruptcy prediction (Journal of Business Economics, Review of Managerial Science, Computational Economics, Review of Quantitative Finance and Accounting, Journal of the Knowledge Economy, Journal of Economics and Finance, Review of Quantitative Finance and Accounting, etc.)

Research methods: quantitative analysis (calculation of financial coefficients (liquidity, profitability, turnover, economic stability, etc.) based on financial reporting data); statistical analysis.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The advent of big data, information technology, and social media provides a huge amount of information about firms' current financial condition. Faced with such an abundance of data, decision makers must identify important information in order to build an effective and operational forecasting model with a high-quality expected result.

C. Lohmann et al. consider additive models to identify and analyze nonlinear relationships between independent variables and how they affect bankruptcy forecasts. The authors show that the bankruptcy forecast is influenced by statistically and economically significant nonlinear relationships [1].

M. Geulen et al. believe that an analysis of an organization's financial performance can predict short-term bankruptcy, but an assessment of management features increases accuracy in the long term [2].

A. Beade et al. consider multi-period bankruptcy forecasting models since lenders must assess the risk of loans over the entire life of the debt rather than at a certain point in the future. The authors consider two possibilities of implementing forecasting models: multi-model, multi-period and single-model, multi-period [3].

H. H. Nguyen et al. write that ensemble machine learning models have recently been widely used and have demonstrated their effectiveness in predicting bankruptcy. The authors evaluate the forecasting efficiency of Random Forest, LightGBM, XGBoost, and NGBoost using the example of French firms from different industries with a 1-5-year horizon [4].

A. Rahmi et al. study the role of total income and its components, in addition to net income, as input data for bankruptcy forecasting. The authors propose a bankruptcy forecasting model using the random forest method [5].

S. Ben Jabeur et al. propose the XGBoost algorithm and compare it with seven machine learning algorithms based on three well-known feature selection methods often used in bankruptcy forecasting: step-by-step discriminant analysis, step-by-step logistic regression, and partial least squares discriminant analysis [6].

M. Fan et al. use ensemble learning models to solve class imbalance problems. The authors propose a comprehensive structure that increases forecasting effectiveness and satisfies external users' interpretability needs [7].

P. du Jardin notes that the data, which represents a firm's financial position measured at a certain point in time, and the variables that can embody this situation are not structured in such a way as to make them suitable for use with convolutional neural networks (CNNs). The authors propose a method to convert data into a topological space to study CNN's ability to predict corporate bankruptcy and financial collapse [8].

P. Arora and S. Saurabh apply modern machine learning methods, such as logistic regression, lasso regression, decision tree, etc., for forecasting tasks [9].

M. Statkova considers the possibility of classifying logistic regression models in bankruptcy forecasting in two production sectors. The author uses two criteria derived from empirically evaluated ROC curves, which allow the error rate in active and bankrupt companies to be balanced [10].

Various methodological tools are used to assess the viability of firms, in particular: logistic and neural network models, by maximizing their discriminatory power, measured by the Area Under Receiver Operating Characteristics (AUROC) curve [11]; a methodological approach based on fuzzy sets and Boolean logic, namely the fuzzy qualitative comparative analysis (fsQCA) method [12], longitudinal predictive model [13]; adjusted present value (APV) methods [14]; biclusterization methods [15]; Altman models [16]; discriminant analysis [17] and other methods [18; 19].

Thus, existing methods and models based on financial ratios may not always provide high accuracy in predicting bankruptcy. It is necessary to identify and analyze the factors that affect the effectiveness of these models, to develop new approaches that can improve their accuracy, to determine the most significant coefficients for predicting bankruptcy, to develop a methodology for combining them to increase the information content of the analysis, and to create dynamic models that consider temporary changes in financial indicators and allow predicting financial difficulties more accurately.

RESULTS

Financial analysis of the organization's activities at the bankruptcy stage using the example of Stroybytservice JSC. The bankruptcy case against Stroybytservice JSC was opened on May 20, 2020.

To calculate the indicators established by the Rules [20], information about the organization must be considered two years before the opening of the bankruptcy case and during the bankruptcy procedure itself. According to the Rules, all indicators are calculated quarterly.

Tables 1 and 2 show the leading economic indicators according to the accounting statements used to calculate financial ratios.

Table 1

The main financial indicators for calculating coefficients two years before the opening of the bankruptcy case, thousand RUR (bankruptcy case dated 05/20/2020)

Name	01.04.2018	01.07.2018	01.10.2018	01.01.2019	01.04.2019	01.07.2019	01.10.2019	01.01.2020	01.04.2020
Total assets (liabilities)	804 788	839 360	885 768	886 970	999 919	1 082 749	1 680 272	1 639 971	1 207 701
Adjusted non-current assets	307 846	300 927	270 735	254 381	255 169	255 747	260 270	259 636	265 000
Current assets	496 942	538 433	615 033	632 589	744 750	827 002	1 420 002	1 380 335	942 701

Long-term accounts receivable	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Most liquid assets	3 409	7 320	11 361	15 303	13 931	11 126	9 127	18 552	7 105
Short-term accounts receivable	308 022	312 515	316 456	320 674	363 892	427 345	676 145	713 064	646 300
Liquid assets	311 431	319 835	327 817	335 977	377 823	438 471	685 272	731 616	653 405
Potential current assets to be returned	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Own funds	87 992	89 693	91 024	93 033	-74 211	-370 831	-560 520	-738 661	-779 917
Obligations of the debtor	730 302	763 020	776 599	793 937	874 433	998 733	1 102 168	1 254 276	1 225 784
Long-term obligations of the debtor	308 611	359 965	401 733	435 973	460 238	500 237	529 072	567 216	531 400
Current obligations	421 691	403 055	374 686	357 964	414 195	498 496	573 096	687 060	694 384
Revenue	354 200	764 410	1 075 086	1 190 705	340 256	624 257	874 582	996 984	48 723
Average monthly revenue	118 066	254 803	358 362	357 211	113 418	208 085	291 527	332 328	16 241
Net profit	22 853	13 728	9 602	6 766	-267 045	-532 672	-807 037	-828 200	-715 001

Table 2

The main financial indicators for calculating coefficients during the bankruptcy procedure, thousand RUR (from 05/20/2020 until the decision to declare the debtor bankrupt)

Naming of the indicator	01.07.2020	01.10.2020	01.01.2021	01.04.2021	01.07.2021	01.10.2021	01.01.2022
Total assets (liabilities)	444 742	313 906	243 038	237 330	219 064	210 692	204 984
Adjusted non-current assets	242 905	172 318	134 084	130 025	127 438	115 167	108 518
Current assets	201 837	141 588	108 954	107 081	103 835	97 841	96 466
Long-term accounts receivable	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Most liquid assets	1 690	1 348	18	18	16	13	8
Short-term accounts receivable	126 869	82 342	58 224	56 643	53 902	48 840	47 681
Liquid assets	128 559	83 690	58 242	56 661	53 918	48 853	47 689
Potential current assets to be returned	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Own funds	-814 597	-844 218	-877 382	-881 275	-883 880	-887 026	-889 969
Obligations of the debtor	1 225 034	1 155 224	1 120 420	1 116 600	1 109 979	1 097 755	1 094 953
Long-term obligations of the debtor	526 545	451 462	410 793	407 793	402 593	392 993	390 793
Current obligations	698 489	703 762	709 627	708 807	707 386	704 762	704 160
Revenue	48 360	56 187	209 094	3 056	1 070	1 789	7 378
Average monthly revenue	16 120	18 729	69 698	1 018	357	596	2 459
Net profit (loss)	(68 950)	(103 837)	(138 721)	(107 447)	(76 173)	(44 899)	(13 623)

Solvency is usually understood as an organization's ability to fulfill its payment obligations on time.

Let us calculate the indicators for assessing the solvency of Sroybytservice JSC using the formulas:

The absolute liquidity ratio is determined by the ratio of the most liquid assets to current liabilities.

The degree of solvency is defined as the ratio of the debtor's current obligations to the average monthly revenue.

The current liquidity ratio is the ratio of liquid assets to current liabilities.

The liability security indicator is defined as the ratio of the amount of liquid and adjusted non-current assets to the debtor's liabilities.

The calculation results are presented in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3

Coefficients of solvency of Sroybytservice JSC before initiation of bankruptcy proceedings
(bankruptcy case dated 05/20/2020)

Naming of the indicator	01.04. 2018	01.07. 2018	01.10. 2018	01.01.2019	01.04.2019	01.07.2019	01.10.2019	01.01.2020	01.04.2020
Absolute liquidity ratio	0.008	0.018	0.03	0.043	0.034	0.022	0.016	0.027	0.01
Current liquidity ratio	0.739	0.794	0.874	0.934	0.912	0.88	1.196	1.065	0.941
Securing the debtor's obligations with his assets	0.848	0.814	0.77	0.743	0.724	0.695	0.858	0.79	0.749
Degree of solvency for current obligations	4	2	1	1	4	2	2	2	43

Table 4

Coefficients of solvency of Sroybytservice JSC during the bankruptcy procedure

Naming of the indicator	01.07.2020	01.10.2020	01.01.2021	01.04.2021	01.07.2021	01.10.2021	01.01.2022
Absolute liquidity ratio	0.002	0.002	0	0	0	0	0
Current liquidity ratio	0.184	0.119	0.082	0.08	0.076	0.069	0.068
Securing the debtor's obligations with his assets	0.303	0.222	0.172	0.167	0.163	0.149	0.143
Degree of solvency for current obligations	43	38	10	696	1981	1182	286

Throughout the analyzed period, the absolute liquidity ratio does not correspond to the recommended value of 0.2-0.25. From the beginning to the end of the analyzed period, the value of this coefficient is zero, which indicates a stable shortage of available funds needed daily to repay at least 20% of current liabilities.

The value of the current liquidity ratio was within the normal range until October 1, 2019. From that moment until the end of the period under review, it was below the lower limit of the regulatory range (1.0-2.0). The coefficient dynamics are gradually deteriorating. The low degree of the enterprise's current liquidity is the first and main sign of the company's insolvency.

"The indicator of the security of the debtor's obligations with his assets characterizes the value of the debtor's assets per unit of debt" [2]. It is recommended that the resulting value be equal to one or greater than one. In our case, the calculated values of the indicator are less than one, which indicates that the organization's obligations are not secured by its assets.

Until April 1, 2020, the solvency index was within the normal range (3-4 months). Starting from April 1, 2020, the indicator is too high. In the current situation, the company has increased its accounts payable, while the revenue volume has decreased. Consequently, the company is unable to meet its payment obligations in a timely and complete manner, i.e., it is insolvent.

Financial stability is understood as the organization's independence from external sources of funds, its ability to manage its own funds efficiently, and its ability to maintain credit discipline.

Let us calculate the financial stability indicators of Stroybyservice JSC using the following formulas:

The coefficient of autonomy is the ratio of own funds to total assets;

Own working capital ratio is the ratio of the difference between own funds and adjusted non-current assets to the value of current assets;

The share of overdue accounts payable in liabilities is the ratio of overdue accounts payable to total liabilities (determined as a percentage).

The ratio of accounts receivable to total assets is the ratio of long-term accounts receivable, short-term accounts receivable, and potential current assets to be returned to the organization's total assets.

The calculation results are presented in Tables 5 and 6.

Table 5

Indicators of the financial stability of Stroybyservice JSC before the initiation of bankruptcy proceedings

Naming of the indicator	01.04. 2018	01.07. 2018	01.10. 2018	01.01.2019	01.04.2019	01.07.2019	01.10.2019	01.01.2020	01.04.2020
Coefficient of autonomy (financial stability)	0.11	0.11	0.1	0.11	-0.07	-0.34	-0.33	-0.45	-0,65

Coefficient of availability of own working capital	-0.44	-0.39	-0.29	-0.26	-0.44	-0.76	-0.58	-0.72	-1,11
Ratio of accounts receivable to total assets	0.38	0.37	0.36	0.36	0.36	0.39	0.4	0.43	0,54

Table 6

Indicators of the financial stability of Stroybytservice JSC during bankruptcy

Name	01.07.2020	01.10.2020	01.01.2021	01.04.2021	01.07.2021	01.10.2021	01.01.2022
Coefficient of autonomy (financial stability)	-1.83	-2.69	-3.61	-3.71	-4.03	-4.21	-4.34
Coefficient of availability of own working capital	-5.23	-7.18	-9.28	-9.44	-9.74	-10.24	-10.35
Share of overdue accounts payable in liabilities, %	4.12	3.96	3.32	3.15	2.89	2.77	2.49
Ratio of accounts receivable to total assets	0.29	0.26	0.24	0.24	0.25	0.23	0.23

The coefficient of autonomy or financial independence shows the proportion of the debtor's assets that their funds secure. It is recommended that the coefficient value be greater than 0.5. Starting from April 1, 2019, own funds have a negative trend. As of April 1, 2019, the uncovered loss amounted to 267,045 thousand rubles, resulting in the indicator assuming a negative value. The debtor does not have a share of assets covered by its capital (provided by its sources of formation), and its assets are fully formed from borrowed funds.

The coefficient of availability of own working capital determines the degree to which an organization is provided with the working capital necessary for its financial stability [21]. The value of this coefficient must be equal to 0.1 or greater than 0.1. The lack of its working capital, i.e., a negative coefficient value, indicates that all the organization's working capital is formed at the expense of accounts payable and borrowed sources of funds. In the assessed organization, the value of this indicator is negative, which indicates that Stroybytservice JSC does not have enough funds to cover non-current assets.

The share of overdue accounts payable in liabilities characterizes the presence of overdue accounts payable and its share in the total liabilities of an organization [22]. It is recommended that the value of this indicator should not exceed 20%. The organization's share of overdue accounts payable in liabilities is above the standard 20%. This indicator has no improvement until the end of the analyzed period; on the contrary, they are getting worse.

This situation indicates signs of bankruptcy of the organization under investigation.

It is believed that the value of the ratio of accounts receivable to total assets should be less than 0.4 [23]. The organization in question does not have long-term accounts receivable, which can be assessed positively. Debtors' debt in the structure of total assets during the analyzed period occupies more than 40% (43% and above), starting from January

1, 2020, in anticipation of the opening of bankruptcy proceedings. During the bankruptcy procedure, the indicator decreases. However, this does not indicate an improvement in the situation, as it is associated with a curtailment of production, a reduction in accounts receivable and total assets.

The third group of coefficients is indicators of the debtor's business activity. These are the return on assets and a simple rate of return. Return on assets is calculated as the ratio of net profit to total assets. The net profit margin is defined as the ratio of net profit to revenue. Let us calculate the indicators in Tables 7 and 8.

Table 7

Calculation of the business activity indicators of Sroybyservice JSC before the initiation of bankruptcy proceedings

Indicators	01.04.2018	01.07.2018	01.10.2018	01.01.2019	01.04.2019	01.07.2019	01.10.2019	01.01.2020	01.04.2020
Revenue	744 256	842 658	956 234	1 190 705	258 458	336 564	478 256	532 569	648 123
Net profit	3 654	4 325	5 450	6 766	528	645	725	818	760
Total assets	804 788	839 360	885 768	886 970	999 919	1 082 749	1 680 272	1 639 971	1 207 701
Return on assets %	0.45	0.52	0.62	0.76	0.05	0.06	0.04	0.05	0,06
Rate of net profit %	0.49	0.51	0.57	0.57	0.2	0.19	0.15	0.15	0,12

Table 8

Calculation of business activity indicators of Sroybyservice JSC during the bankruptcy procedure

Indicators	01.07.2020	01.10.2020	01.01.2021	01.04.2021	01.07.2021	01.10.2021	01.01.2022
Revenue	48 360	56 187	209 094	3 056	4 070	5 789	7 378
Net profit (loss)	(68 950)	(103 837)	(138 721)	(10 447)	(11 173)	(12 899)	(13 623)
Total assets	444 742	313 906	243 038	237 330	219 064	210 692	204 984
Return on assets %	-15.5	-33.08	-57.08	-4.4	-5.1	-6.12	-6.65
Rate of net profit %	-142.58	-184.81	-66.34	-341.85	-287.79	-222.82	-184.64

According to Table 7, Sroybyservice JSC was profitable before the bankruptcy case was initiated. Business activity indicators are minimal, but at least they represent positive values. Starting from July 1, 2020 and until the end of the period under review, the organization incurs losses, respectively, business activity indicators throughout this period take on negative values.

The break-even point is the point where the revenue from sales is equal to the total cost, i.e. there is no profit or loss. The break-even point determines what the sales volume should be in order for the company to cover all its expenses without making a profit.

Table 9

The initial data for the calculation (according to the accounting statements)

Indicators	Amount, thousand RUR
Cost of work performed	48 798
Including:	
variable costs	306
fixed costs	48 492
Proceeds from the sale of completed works	7 378

The break-even point formula is determined by the following formula:

$$T_B = \frac{Z_{post}}{B - Z_{per}} * B$$

where:

T_B is the break-even point in monetary terms;

Z_{post} is fixed costs;

B is revenue from the sale of completed works;

Z_{per} is variable cost.

Calculate the break-even point:

$$T_B = (48\,492 / (7\,378 - 306)) * 7\,378 = 50\,583,56 \text{ thousand RUR.}$$

In order for the company to overcome the crisis and cover all losses, the volume of work (services) performed should be 50 583.56 thousand RUR.

Considering the fact that Stroybytservice JSC does not actually carry out any activities due to the lack of large orders, the debtor's break-even activity is impossible.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the analysis of the debtor's solvency coefficients, it follows that Stroybytservice JSC does not have enough working capital, the organization is unable to repay short-term debt in a timely manner, even with the help of the sale of its own assets. Based on the above, the coefficient analysis gives us the opportunity to determine the current state of Stroybytservice JSC as a crisis. As a result of the analysis of the debtor's financial stability coefficients, it can be seen that the debtor's activities are completely dependent on external sources of financing.

Due to the fact that the debtor has reduced virtually all staff, there are no new contracts for the performance of works (services), the debtor's business reputation has been damaged by litigation due to poor-quality work, and the introduction of bankruptcy restoration procedures (external management, financial rehabilitation) is impractical.

On April 28, 2022, the Arbitration Court issued a decision in the case of declaring Stroybytservice JSC bankrupt, terminating the monitoring procedure and introducing bankruptcy proceedings. According to the final report of the monitoring procedure, the following was established:

Signs of deliberate bankruptcy have been identified;

No signs of fictitious bankruptcy have been identified;

It is impossible to restore the debtor's solvency;

The debtor has the necessary funds to cover the court costs and the costs of paying the manager's remuneration.

The court's decision to open bankruptcy proceedings is correct and justified.

CONCLUSION

With global economic changes, fluctuations in financial markets, and instability in various industries, including construction, the need for effective bankruptcy prediction tools is becoming increasingly important.

With the development of technologies such as machine learning and big data, new opportunities are opening up for deeper and more accurate analysis of financial ratios. This allows us to develop more complex bankruptcy prediction models, which makes the topic relevant for researchers and practitioners.

The prospects of the topic also lie in the possibility of integrating the analysis of financial coefficients with other methods, such as the analysis of external factors (economic, political, social) and qualitative analysis.

Research in this area can lead to the development of practical recommendations for construction companies to improve their financial condition and prevent bankruptcy. This can be useful for both managers and investors.

The topic may be relevant not only within one country, but also in an international context. A comparative analysis of financial ratios and bankruptcy prediction models in different countries can open up new horizons for research.

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